

CHANGES IN MORPHOLOGICAL AND MORPHOMETRIC PARAMETERS OF THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE OF THE GASTRIC LINING OF ADULT RATS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUGS

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Abstract: Recent years have also seen the development of smartphone applications such as "My Medicine Passport" to improve communication between patients and health care providers, improve people's understanding of their condition and treatment, and track changes to a patient's medication.

As the population ages in the developed world, particularly the UK, the number of people with chronic conditions is increasing, and there is increasing pressure on doctors to adhere to evidence-based guidelines for the management of chronic conditions.

Despite the fact that many researches are carried out in polypragmasy, information about the stomach, which is the central organ of the alimentary canal, is very little in the literature.

Key words: morphology, stomach, mucous membrane, morphometry.

INTRODUCTION. By the middle of the 21st century, diseases of the gastrointestinal system occupy one of the leading places among common chronic diseases [erosive-gastritis and erosive-ulcer gastritis] [73, P.140-153], therefore, in recent years, the histological structure of the gastric mucosa of humans and mammals is being studied. In particular, new directions have been identified in the study of albino rats, since rats are the main model for reproducing human pathology under experimental conditions and for testing new drugs.

All of the above undoubtedly makes it difficult to correctly interpret the functional significance of the components of the stomach wall in normal and pathological terms.

Central to previous research on polypharmacy is the need to manage the risks and benefits of drug treatment. This is an area where "personalized medicine" approaches can help. In recent decades, the healthcare system is gradually moving from reactive to preventive, to an individual approach to medicine [111, S.117-118].

This new approach to healthcare will ultimately provide patients and physicians with personalized information about each individual's unique health experience. This information helps to personalize care based on each person's unique characteristics. This approach can be developed by supporting "digital patient communities" that allow patients to communicate with other patients with similar long-term illnesses and learn from other patients' experiences [140, R.350].

The relevance and necessity of studying the problems is very clear, because it is very important to reveal the

adaptation mechanisms and morphological bases of the gastric mucosa, and this allows to determine the morphological and morphometric characteristics at different ages.

From the above literature review, it is clear that there is insufficient research on polypharmacy and its effects on the gastrointestinal system. There are some inconsistencies among the available data, which require further morphological and morphometric investigations.

Materials and methods of research. The study of the macromorphology of the stomach, the micromorphology of the mucosa and the submucosal base was carried out in 180 5-month-old white male rats under normal vivarium conditions.

The following anti-inflammatory agents were used to study the effects of polypharmacy in experimental groups of white-bred rats:

Aspirin (derivatives of NSAID-salicylic acid), paracetamol (derivatives of NSAID-anilides), ibuprofen (derivatives of NSAID-propionic acid), dexamethasone (synthetic glucocorticosteroid), (plaquenil sulfate - an antimalarial drug with an inflammatory effect).

White rats taken for the experiment were divided into 5 groups (n=180): I-group – (intact) control (n=20); Group II - white rats that received 2 different anti-inflammatory drugs, paracetamol 15 mg/kg, aspirin 5 mg/kg (n=40); III - group - white rats that received 3 different anti-inflammatory drugs, paracetamol 15 mg/kg, aspirin 5 mg/kg, ibuprofen 6 mg/kg (n=40); Group IV - white rats that received 4 different anti-inflammatory drugs, paracetamol 15 mg/kg, aspirin 5 mg/kg, ibuprofen 6 mg/kg, dexamethasone 0.1 mg/kg. (n=40); Group B - white rats that received 4 different nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, paracetamol 15 mg/kg, aspirin 5 mg/kg, ibuprofen 6 mg/kg, dexamethasone 0.1 mg/kg, hydroxychloroquine sulfate 6.5 mg/kg (n=40). Doses of this drug were calculated empirically and were injected into the stomach every day for 10 days.

From day 141 to day 150 of development, rats in the control group of white male rats were injected with 0.5 ml of distilled water intragastrically for 10 days.

Results of our own research. 5 different types of anti-inflammatory drugs [paracetamol 15 mg/kg, aspirin 5 mg/kg, ibuprofen 6 mg/kg, dexamethasone 0.1 mg/kg, hydroxychloroquine sulfate] were administered to 5 groups of white male rats, which were laboratory animals, during the five-month period. 6.5 mg/kg] after the administration of the morphological and morphometric parameters of the stomach wall revealed the following data:

The gastric wall is one of the main components, the cardiac part of the mucous membrane of the organ has a height of 382.4 - 467.3 μm , and the average was $434.0 \pm 7.8 \mu\text{m}$. The height of the mucous membrane at the bottom of the organ varied from 443.4 to 474.9 μm , and the average was $470.6 \pm 2.4 \mu\text{m}$. The height of this layer in the body of the stomach ranged from 451.2 to 492.7 μm , and the average was $478.4 \pm 3.8 \mu\text{m}$. The height of the mucous membrane in the pyloric part is 382.4 - 423.7 μm , on average - $400.9 \pm 3.8 \mu\text{m}$.

During the histological analysis of the elastic fibers of the cardiac part, it was found that they are firmly located between the folds of the mucous membrane. In the area of the fold base of the mucous membrane, tufts of elastic fibers are characterized by their direction in different directions. The direction of the bundles of elastic fibers of the pyloric part has a longitudinal orientation, the part of the bundles close to the glands changes its direction and separates them from each other, like barriers. Along the periphery of vessels with their plate, bundles of elastic fibers take a circular direction. The height of the fold of the cardiac part of the stomach wall was 361.3-428.2 μm , and its average value was $416.4 \pm 6.1 \mu\text{m}$ [Fig. 3.11].

In the area of the bottom, this indicator is 373.1-441.3 μm , on average - $425.6 \pm 6.2 \mu\text{m}$. The height of the fold of the body part of the stomach wall was 382.1-456.3 μm , and the average was $439.5 \pm 6.8 \mu\text{m}$. And in

the area of transition to the duodenum [pyloric part], this indicator was 337.1-391.4 μm , the average was 377.1 \pm 5.01 μm .

The height of the cavity between the folds of the mucous membrane, which is one of the components of the stomach wall, was 318.4-400.6 μm in the cardiac part, and its average value was 386.5 \pm 6.7 μm . It can be seen that it varies from 315.1 to 395.3 μm in the area of the bottom, and the average is equal to 386.1 \pm 7.1 μm . (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Picture. Structure of gastric wall cardiac part of five-month-old group V white rats.

1 - mucosal layer, 2 - submucosa base, 3-muscular layer. Stain hematoxylin-eosin. Size.10X20.

When studying the body part of the stomach wall, this indicator was equal to 285.6-395.3 μm , the average - 318.5 \pm 8.4 μm . In the pyloric part of the member, the height of the groove between the studied folds was 229.3-321.7 μm , the average - 270.2 \pm 7.6 μm . The thickness of the submucosa base under the mucous layer of the stomach wall in the cardiac area of the organ varied from 29.2 to 38.4 μm , and the average was 38.2 \pm 0.85 μm . The thickness of the submucosal base at the bottom of the organ varied from 30.3 to 37.1 μm , and the average was equal to 35.5 \pm 0.62 μm . The thickness of the submucosa base in the body part of the stomach wall ranged from 31.4 to 40.6 μm , and the average was 36.3 \pm 0.85 μm . The thickness of this layer in the pyloric part of the organ varied from 32.8 to 44.5 μm , and the average was 38.9 \pm 1.1 μm . The thickness of the total muscle layer of the stomach wall in the cardiac part of the organ was 228.2-251.3 μm [Fig. 3.11], the average was equal to 235.9 \pm 2.12 μm . The thickness of the muscle layer at the bottom was between 182.4-224.6 μm , and the average was -203.8 \pm 3.9 μm . The thickness of the muscle layer of the body part of the stomach wall was 197.1-236.5 μm , the average was 226.1 \pm 3.62 μm . [Figure 3.12]. (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Structure of gastric wall and body part of five-month-old group V white rats. 1 - mucosal layer, 2 - submucosa base, 3-muscular layer. Stain hematoxylin-eosin. The size is 10X40.

The structural elements of the special plate of the mucous membrane of the stomach wall are reflected in the connective tissue fibers. A characteristic feature of the private plate of collagen fibers is that their bundles have different directions in the cardiac part. In the spaces between the folds of the mucous membrane, bundles of collagen fibers are oriented longitudinally. In the folds of the mucus, they change their orientation and have different directions. (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Cardiac part of the stomach of group V white rats. 1 - mucosal layer, 2 - submucosa base, 3 - muscle layer, 4 - a cavity between folds. Paint Van – Gizon. Size.10X20.

In the transition to the duodenum, this indicator ranged from 366.4 to 423.2 μm , and the average was equal to $403.5 \pm 5.2 \mu\text{m}$. The height of the gland tissue of the gastric wall in the cardiac part was from 19.8 to 25.9 μm , the average was $24.3 \pm 0.56 \mu\text{m}$. This indicator varies from 25.1 to 31.4 μm in the area of the bottom of the organ, the average is $21.0 \pm 0.58 \mu\text{m}$. The height of glandular tissue of the body part was in the range of 23.4-28.1 μm , and the average was $26.4 \pm 0.43 \mu\text{m}$. In the pyloric part, this parameter was equal to 28.2-31.6 μm , on average - $30.2 \pm 0.31 \mu\text{m}$. The total thickness of the stomach wall in the cardiac part of the organ varied from 671.3 to 789.9 μm , and its average value was $732.2 \pm 10.9 \mu\text{m}$. It varied from 634.5 to 762.3 μm in the area of the bottom, and was equal to $722.6 \pm 11.7 \mu\text{m}$ on average. The total thickness of the stomach wall in the organ body ranged from 729.4 to 772.6 μm , and the average was $756.5 \pm 3.9 \mu\text{m}$. In the pyloric part, this indicator was 764.1-889.6 μm , the average was $858.8 \pm 11.5 \mu\text{m}$ the fourth and by 25.2% in the fifth group, respectively.

In the pyloric region, the distance between glandular tissues in the control group averaged $25.46 \pm 0.59 \text{ mm}$, in the second group the distance between glandular tissues increased to 28.6 ± 0.65 , in the third group 30.3 ± 0.59 , in the fourth group 33.1 ± 0.57 and increased to $41.6 \pm 0.93 \text{ mm}$ in the fifth and last group

CONCLUSION. Under the influence of different amounts of anti-inflammatory drugs, different degrees of morphological changes occur in the stomach. Due to the decrease in the size of the gastric mucosa and the submucosal base after the effect of drugs, the total thickness of the gastric wall was significantly reduced in groups 4-5. These changes were 1.60% in the cardiac part of 4 groups of laboratory animals, 3.27% in the stomach bottom, 3.33% in the body and 3.65% in the pyloric part, while in 5 groups of laboratory animals it was 2.21% in the cardiac part of the organ. %, changed to 3.89% in the base, 3.0% in the body of the stomach and 5.2% in the pyloric part.

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